

USING AUTHENTIC MATERIALS TO ASSESS LINGUISTIC COMPETENCE IN HIGH SCHOOL LEARNERS

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***Abstract.** Nowadays, knowledge of a foreign language, specifically English, is becoming necessary – computer, economic and political terminology are based on English. The socio-economic changes that have taken place and are taking place in our country have led to a decisive revision of the place and role of a foreign language in the life of society.*

***Keywords.** Game, developmental education, primary school, skills, intellectual abilities, social competencies.*

Introduction. The change in the status of a foreign language in the school system has influenced the rearrangement of priorities in the work of foreign language teachers. In this connection, it became necessary to change the approach to teaching, specifically, to teach a foreign language in Russian schools, namely, to form communicative competence. The main purpose of learning foreign languages at school, according to the Federal State Educational Standard for Basic General Education, is the formation of foreign language communicative competence among schoolchildren: the ability and willingness to carry out foreign language education interpersonal and intercultural communication with native speakers. Foreign language communicative competence also provides for the development of communicative skills in the main types of speech activity: speaking, listening comprehension, reading and writing.

Communicative competence is integrative and includes several components:

- communicative skills in speaking, listening, reading and writing;
- knowledge and skills of language material for obtaining information;

– linguistic and regional knowledge to ensure secondary socialization, and socio-cultural background, without which it is impossible to form a communicative competence.

Authentic materials are one of the important sources of obtaining linguistic, regional and cultural information to expand the socio-cultural background. The analysis of domestic and foreign methodological literature has revealed a great potential for attracting authentic materials as a means of teaching English. This fact determines the relevance of our chosen research topic. It is known that the purpose of teaching a foreign language is the formation of communicative competence, which includes both

linguistic and socio-cultural competence. Learning a foreign language is designed to form a person who is able and willing to participate in intercultural communication. By the new target settings, the task of a foreign language teacher is to provide conditions for introducing the student's personality to foreign language culture and effective participation in the dialogue of cultures. Therefore, in a foreign language lesson, a special place should be given to such forms of classes that ensure the active participation of each student in the lesson, stimulate speech communication, and contribute to the formation of interest and desire to learn a foreign language. One of the effective ways to solve these problems facing every teacher of a foreign language, without exception, is to use authentic materials. The main difficulty associated with the use of authentic materials in the process of teaching a foreign language is, of course, their insufficient language accessibility for most students. One of the main and widespread solutions to this problem is their previous methodological processing (adaptation), which reduces the gap between their level of linguistic complexity and the level of language training of students. The question of the expediency of processing the original foreign language materials is very controversial. "Adaptation cannot be understood" is how N.V. Kulibina interprets her article on the problem of adapting

literary texts for use in the process of teaching a foreign language, and these words aptly express the complexity and inconsistency of this situation.

Conclusion. Thus, in addition, it should be emphasized that for modern society it is important to teach a natural and, most importantly, a modern foreign language, which is possible only if materials taken from the life of native speakers or compiled taking into account the peculiarities of their culture and mentality by accepted and used speech norms are used. The use of similar educational and authentic materials, which are natural speech work created for methodological purposes, will make it possible to effectively provide training in all types of speech activity, in particular, oral communication in a foreign language, simulate immersion in a natural speech environment in foreign language classes.

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